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Emerging Trends and Challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the emerging trends and challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities with particular emphasis on artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Thing (Io). The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 512 final year Business Education students from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Because of the manageable size of the population. The entire population was studied as sample size. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Emerging Trends and Challenges in Business Education Questionnaire (EPCBEQ). The instrument was validated by three experts, and the reliability was ascertained, using Cronbach Alpha statistics to be 0.92 out of 512 questionnaire distributed, 432 were retrieved and used for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while t-test hypotheses statistics were used to test the hypothesis. The findings revealed that business education students perceive artificial intelligence (AI) as helpful in reducing learning challenges by enhancing personalized learning, improving understanding of complex concepts, and supporting independent learning. The study also found that the internet of things (IOT) contributes to addressing challenges in Business Education by improving real-time access to learning resources, enhancing practical learning experience and strengthening communication and interaction in learning environment. The researchers recommended that Business Education department should intensify the integration of AI tools and IOT systems to enhance teaching and learning, improve student performance, and better prepare graduates for the digital economy.

Keywords: AI, Emerging Trend, challenges, Business Education, Internet of Things.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the convergence of technological innovation and globalization has posed unprecedented challenges and opportunities for Business Education. With the repaid proliferation of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and the internet of Things (IoT), traditional business curricula, which primarily focus on theoretical foundations, struggle to equip students with the dynamic and practical skill required by modern industries in gradually phasing out. The advent of Industry 4.0 has transformed business landscapes, placing a premium on graduates who possess not only technical proficiency but also adaptability, analytical acumen, and the capacity to navigate data-Intensive environments (Zashchitina & Pavlov, 2020; Mandell, 2022). As a result, business schools are increasingly challenged to evolve, integrating advanced technologies into their educational models and creating curricula that respond to a data-centric, technology-driven world (Christy & Lyau, 2022). Moreover, the rapid pace of technological and market changes underscores the need for continues professional development, a requirement that has

led to the raise of lifelong learning as a central theme in Business Education. Flexible education models, including digital credentials and micro-credentials, have emerged as value solutions for professionals seeking to update their skills and remain competitive in the job market. Business schools, are thus, embracing adoptive learning platforms and online education systems, enabling continuous skill enhancement beyond traditional degree programs (Schlegelmilch, 2020). This focus on lifelong learning represents a shift towards a more learner-centered model, allowing individuals to engage in continuous, personalized educational learning that align with evolving career demands (Castaneda & Cuella, 2021).

Emerging trends refer to new developments, patterns, and innovative approaches that are gradually gaining prominence and are expected to significantly influence various aspects of social, including education, business, and technology. These trends often arise from continuous changes in knowledge, practices, and global demands, and they provide improved and more efficient ways of performing tasks compared to traditional methods. (Larson, 2021). Emerging trends are dynamic in nature, as they evolve over time and snap how individuals and organizations operate in an increasingly complex and competitive environment. Emerging trends have contributed to the globalization of education by promoting accessibly, collaboration, and knowledge sharing across different regions of the world. Learners are no longer confined to traditional classroom settings, as new learning environment allow for greater interactions, creativity, and innovation. Educators, on the other hand, are required to continuously update their teaching methods, and adopt to new developments in order to remain effective in learning instruction. Emerging trends play a crucial role in shaping modern society by introduction, innovation ways of thinking and operating. Their influence continues to expand across different sector, making it essential for individuals and organizations to remain adaptable and responsive to change in order to achieve sustainable growth and development (Mandell, 2022).

Emerging trends in Business Education refers to the evolving innovation and models approaches that continuous to reshape teaching, learning, and skill development in the field. This trends are generally described as new developments or the continuous advancement of existing practices and approaches in education. Emerging trends are designed to prepare graduates for a variety of careers in high-tech business environments (Ogundele & Lawal, 2016). The Business Dictionary (2023) viewed emerging trends as environments that are currently evolving or expected to develop within the next five to ten years and are capable of significantly impacting the business and social environment. These trends provide improved ways of performing tasks emerged to traditional methods. Onojetah and Utoware (2019) optioned that the introduction of emerging trends has made activities around the globe easier, more and result-oriented, leading to the digitalization of many aspects of the daily life.

In the context of education, emerging trends have become a major driving force behind the transformation of teaching and learning process. The rapid advancement of knowledge and the increase demand for relevant skills have necessitated the adoption of modern approaches that enhance learning outcomes and prepare students for real-world challenges. These trends include the integration of digital tools, flexible learning system, interdisciplinary studies, and competency-based education, all of which aim to improve the quality and relevance of education (Suthinanh & Pattarawat, 2005).

In Business Education, emerging trends such as digital learning platforms, online education, data analytics, and artificial intelligence have significantly transformed instructional delivery and learning processes (Bosede, 2020). These developments have improved how institutions operate and how students acquire relevant business skills. In recent times, many educational institutions, including colleges and universities, have increasingly adopted online and blended learning programme. Through emerging trends, educators now employ innovative teaching strategies that enhance effective job performance. Oguejiofor and Ezeanyanwu (2019) stated that these trends enable organizations and their employees to become more productive and efficient in executing specific tasks.

Furthermore, these trends have revolutionaries use not only job performance but also personal lifestyles, as individuals increasingly rely on digital tools in both professional and everyday activities. Ogundele and Lawal (2018), noted that the emerging technology has brought about significant changes in the ways people perform tasks. Despite these positive development, business faces several changes in adapting to emerging trend. These challenges include inadequate technological infrastructure, lack of digital skills

among educators, and students, high cost of implementation, and resistance to change. In many developing countries, limited access to reliable internet services and modern technological tools hinders the effective integration of these innovations into Business Education. Additionally, the rapid pace of advancement associated with emerging trends requires continuous training and up skilling of both teachers and students, which can be difficult to sustain. Ugorji (2019) asserted that since emerging trends are widely reflected in modern workplaces, graduates must develop the ability to adopt to these trends in order to remain competent in the world of work. Despite the numerous benefits associated with emerging trends, there are also challenges that accompany their adoption. These include the need for adequate infrastructure, continuous training, financial resources, and the ability to adopt to constant changes.

However, the successful integration of emerging trends can lead to improved productivity, enhance learning experiences, and better preparation of individuals for future opportunities. The potential of emerging trends in Business Education such as artificial intelligence, learning analytics, the internet of things, and cyber security is to unlock hidden potentials by encouraging the physical improvement of learners learning cognitive skills. Veletsianos (2023) stated that emerging technologies include artificial intelligence adoptive learning, learning analytics, 3D printing, live streaming, learning games and simulations, wearable technologies, massive online open courses, machine learning, and immersion learning similarly, Jason (2023), listed the following as the top five emerging technologies in 2023: Artificial Intelligence (AI), block chain, intelligence automation and robotics, the internet of things (IOT), Quantum, and computing. Given credence to the above-listed emerging technologies, Enang (2022) stated that the need to prepare Business Education students to fit in to the world of work in the 21st century and beyond requires the application of these emerging technologies in the teaching and learning of Business Education programmes. It is worthy to note that the emphasis of this study was placed on the following emerging technologies Artificial Intelligence (AI), and internet of things (IOT).

Artificial intelligence refers to the replication of human intelligence patterns by computer systems, codes, or machines to act and reason like humans. This implies that computers or machines are made to think like human and act rationally to solve problems (Bupo & Akpomi, 2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems, and therefore it is a set of computers inspired by the way humans use their nervous system and their body to feel, learn, and act. (Harkut & Kasat, 2019). AI application are important in the field of human endeavor. But in recent years it has become more important in the field of education, especially higher institution. The mandate of higher institutions transcend the traditional function of preserving heritage, identity, and education. It is rather required to keep pace with emerging technological development through the creation of new methods of education and teaching. Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative technology with profound implications across various domains on like the internet of Things (IoT).

The term internet of Things (IOT) refers to the collection of network of connected devices and technologies that facilitate communication between devices and the cloud, as well as between the devices themselves. The internet of things describes with sensors, processing abilities, software, and other technologies that connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over the internet or other communications network. Alexander (2024) stated that iot is a network of interrelated devices that connect and exit age data with a-to devices and the cloud. The internet of Things (IoT) encompasses electronic communication, computer science, and engineering. IoT has the potential to add tremendous value to institutions of higher learning Educational institutions have great opportunities to benefit from IoT systems. Students may be given smart cards with IoTs. Students can obtain access to the grounds, laboratories, classrooms, libraries, etc. by using these smart cards (Vinayachandra & Krishna, 2022).

Moreover, the rapid technological and market changes underscores the need for continuous professional development, a requirement that has led to the rise of lifelong learning as a central theme in Business Education. Business schools are thus embracing adaptive learning platforms and online education systems, enabling continuous skill enhancement beyond traditional degree programs (Schlogelmich, 2020, Mandell, 2022). This focus on lifelong learning represents a shift towards a moral learner-centered model, allowing individuals to engage in continuous, personalized education journeys that align with evolving

career demands (Castaneda & Cuellar, 2021). However, the global shift towards a technology integrated, flexible Business Education system is not without its challenges. For institutions in resource-constrained settings, limited access to digital tools and expertise gap among faculty members present significant obstacles to implementing these advanced educational models (Smith, 2017).

Bridging this divide requires collaboration efforts from government, private sectors, and academic institutions, along with policies aimed at supporting equitable access to digital learning technologies and faculty development initiatives (Wajdock, 2020). Without such support, the benefits of these emerging educational models may remain concentrated in resourced regions, exacerbating existing disparities in access to quality Business Education.

Challenges in Business Education refer to the various constraints and obstacles that hinder the effective delivery of quality teaching, learning, and skill acquisition in the field. In the 21st century, business education is expected to equip learners with relevant knowledge, practical competences, and digital skills needed to function effectively in a dynamic and technology-driven business environment. However, despite its importance, the system continues to face numerous challenges that affect its ability to meet global standards and labour market demands (Pattarawat, 2025).

One of the major challenges confronting Business Education is the rapid pace of technological changes, which requires continuous curriculum review and integration of modern tools such as digital platforms, data analytics, and artificial intelligence. Many institutions struggle to keep up with these developments due to limited resources and inadequate infrastructure (World Bank, 2022), similarly, the lack of adequately trained instructors with up-to-date technological competencies poses a significant barrier to effective teaching and learning (UNESCO, 2023). Another critical challenge is inadequate funding, which affects the provision of essential facilities such as modern classrooms, computer laboratories, and reliable internet rooms. In many developing countries, insufficient funding limits the adoption of innovative teaching approaches and restricts students' exposure to practical learning experiences (OECD, 2021). The situation is further compounded by overcrowded classrooms and poor learning environment which negatively impact the quality of education delivered.

In addition, there is a growing concern about the mismatch between the skills desired by graduates and the expectations of employers. Many Business Education programmes are theory-based, with limited emphasis on practical and entrepreneurial skills required in today's workplace (International Labour Organization, 2022). This gap reduces graduates' employability and their ability to adapt to real-world business challenges. Resistance to change is another challenge affecting Business Education. Both educators and institutions may be reluctant to adopt new technologies, and curriculum reforms due to fear of uncertainty or lack of awareness. Furthermore, issues such as limited access to digital devices, poor internet connectivity, and high cost of technological tools continue to hinder the effective integration of modern trends into Business Education (UNESCO, 2023), while Business Education remains a vital tool for economic development and workforce preparation, it is faced with several challenges that must be addressed to enhance its effectiveness. Addressing issues such as inadequate funding, technological gaps, skill mismatches, and resistance to innovation is essential for improving the quality and relevance of Business Education in the modern world.

Business Education is an essential aspect of vocational education that provides a solid foundation of knowledge and skills both old and new generations of learners. Business Education is an aspect of vocational education that prepares students to enter the workforce as capable and intelligent members of the teaching and office occupations (Ikenga & Egbule, 2023). Business Education was originally designed to offer students the opportunity to develop the desired abilities, skills, and understanding of the occupational opportunities available in the world of work (Akpomi & Kayii, 2020). Business Education is a process of instructing a person on what happens during business transactions in offices, banks, markets, and anywhere. Money changes hands. Business Education is a field of study designed to develop youth with appropriate skills and competences in business practices. It involves teaching students the fundamentals, concepts, theories, and process of Business (Akpomi, Ubulom & Markson, 2023). Business Education is a course that prepares students for entry into advancement in jobs within business and it is equally important because it prepares students to handle their own business affairs and to function intelligently as consumers and citizens in a business economy (Koko & Chike 2020).

Statement of the problem

The rapid evolution of emerging trade in Business Education particularly the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), has significantly transformed learning and makes skills acquisition compulsory in educational system. These innovations have introduced new opportunities for enhancing instructional delivery, improving students' analytical capabilities, and preparing graduates for participation in a technology-driven global economy. AI for instance, enables personalized learning, delivery of academic tasks, and data-driven decision-making, while IoT facilitates real-time data collection, smart learning environments, and improved interaction between devices audience. Those benefits have the potential to make Business Education practical and aligned with industry demands.

Despite these advantages, the effective integration of AI and IoT into Business Education remains a major challenge especially in developing countries. Many institutions face constraints such as inadequate technological infrastructure, insufficient funding, poor internet connectivity, and lack of access to modern digital tools. In addition, there is problem of quality educators who possess the technical expertise required to effectively utilize AI and IoT in teaching and learning processes. This skills gap limits the ability of institutions to fully harness the benefits of these emerging trends. Furthermore, the high cost of implementing AI and IoT technologies poses a serious barrier to their adoption in Business Education. Institutions are often unable to afford the necessary hardware, software, and maintenance required for effective utilization other barriers are resistance to change among educators who are reluctant to move away from traditional teaching methods and concerns about data privacy, security, and ethical issues surrounding the use of AI, further complicate its integration into educational system.

Another critical problem is the mismatch between the skills acquired by students and the competencies required in modern workplaces. Although AI and IoT offer opportunities for developing relevant digital and analytical skills, their limited implementation in many institutions means that graduates are often inadequately prepared to meet current industry expectations. This situation negatively affects employability and reduces the overall effectiveness of Business Education in achieving its objectives. Therefore, while emerging trends such as AI and IoT present significant benefits for improving Business Education, the numerous challenges associated with their adoption hinder their full utilization. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to examine the emerging trends and challenges in Business Education, with particular emphasis on artificial intelligent and the internet of Things, in order to identify strategies for enhancing their effective integration and improving educational outcomes.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine Emerging Trends and Challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which Business Education students' perceive artificial intelligence (AI) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities
2. Determine the extent to which Business Education students' perceive Internet of Things (IoT) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do Business Education students' perceive artificial intelligence (AI) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities?
2. To what extent do Business Education students' perceive Internet of Things (IoT) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Business Education students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Business Education students perceive artificial intelligence (AI) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Business Education students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Business Education students perceive Internet of Things (IoT) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive research design, which established the significance difference between Emerging Trends and challenges in Business Education students in Rivers State Universities. The study’s population consists of 512 final year Business Education students in Rivers State-owned Universities that offer Business Education, which includes 111 students in 2025/2026 academic session from Rivers State University, and 401 students in 2025/2026 academic session from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, both located in Port Harcourt. The population is chosen because these universities provide Business Education programmes that incorporate Emerging Trends and challenges in Business Education. Due to the management size of the population, no sampling technique was used, the entire population of 512 was studied as sample size of the study out of 512 questionnaires distributed, 432 were retrieved and used for data analysis, 361 from IAUE and 71 from. RSU Questionnaire on Emerging Trends and challenges in Business Education (QETCBE), was used for data collection. This instrument underwent face and content validation by three experts in business education from the Faculty of Education at Rivers State Universities, Port Harcourt. These experts reviewed and restructured the instrument for clarity, relevance, and appropriateness. All input from the experts were used to modify the research instrument. The study used a 4-point rating scale; High Extent (HE-4points), Moderate Extent (ME-3-points) Low Extent (LE-2point) and Very Low Extent (VLE-1-point). Each research question item was based on the real limited scores achieved from the views of the respondents in each table as.

To establish the instruments reliability, the instrument was administered to 30 Business Education standards in Uniport that are not part of the study, test-retest method using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied and a reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the study. Data collected were organized and analyzed based on the research questions and hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation, while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. The boundary limit for the research questions are: High Extent (3.50-4.00), Moderate Extent (2.50-3.00), Low Extent (1.56-2.00) Very High Extent (0.50-1.00). The null hypotheses was accepted if the critical t-value was greater than the calculated t-value; otherwise rejected.

ANALYSIS OF DATA, RESULTS AND HYPOTHESES TESTING

Research Question 1: *To what extent do Business Education students’ perceive Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a challenge in Business Education in Rives State Universities?*

Table 1.1 Mean Responses on the extent do Business Education students’ perceive artificial intelligence (AI) challenges in Business Education in Rives State Universities?

S/N	Items- statement	X	S.D	Remarks
1	I possess the ability to use AI in paragraphing sentence	3.30	0.74	ME
2	I possess the ability to use AI apply in checking plagiarism level	3.55	0.60	HE
3	I possess the ability to apply AI in clarifying complex topics	3.40	0.49	ME
4	I possess the ability to apply AI in doing your assignment	2.51	0.69	ME
5	I possess the ability to apply AI in paraphrasing sentence	3.31	0.61	ME
6	I possess the ability to apply AI in your seminar research	3.42	0.69	ME
Grand Mean &SD		3.25	0.64	ME

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The result in table 1 shows that Business Education students’ perceive artificial intelligence (AI) as a challenge in Business Education in Rivers State Universities to a moderate extent. Item 1,3,4,5 shows

moderate extent, except for item 2 that show high extent. The result shows that artificial intelligence as an aspect of emerging trends play an important role in shaping Business Education programme.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do Business Education students’ perceive Internet of Things (IoT) as a challenge in Business Education in Rives State Universities?*

Table 1.2 Mean Responses on the extent to which Business Education students’ perceive Internet of Things (IoT) as a challenge in Business Education in Rives State Universities

(N = 4.32)

S/N	Items – students	\bar{X}	S D	Remarks
7	I possess the ability to apply smart TV or use internet on phone	3.56	0.76	ME
8	IoT enable automatic control of devices and systems, reducing human effort and increasing efficiency in homes, businesses, and industries	3.13	0.78	HE
9	IoT devices collect and transmit data instantly, allowing uses to monitor activities and make quick informed decisions?	3.30	0.72	ME
10	With access to accurate and timely data, I can analyze trends and improve planning, and overall decision-making in academics	3.43	0.60	ME
11	IoT helps reduce operational costs by optimizing resource use, minimizing waste and preventing system failures through predictive maintenance?	2.89	0.61	ME
12	I possess the ability to apply interactive white board in teaching and learning?	3.57	0.80	ME
13	I possess the ability to apply IoT in remote learning	3.17	0.57	ME
Grand Mean & S D		3.29	0.72	ME

Source: SPSS Version 23 (2026)

Data contained in table 1.2 shows that some or significance percent of Business Education students’ perceive Internet of Things (IoT) challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities as helpful in the 21st century with moderate extent. Item two and seven show a high extent, other items show to a moderate extent. With all the items above 2.50 and mean score of 3.29 and Standard Deviation 0.72 respectively.

Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1: There is no significance in the mean rating of Business Education students in Rivers Universities and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Business Education students’ perceive artificial intelligence (AI) challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities.

Table 1:3: Computation of difference in mean rating: between Business Education students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Business Education students’ perceive artificial intelligence (AI) challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	t-crit.	Df	α	Decision
RSU	71	3.53	0.22	1.875	1.516	4.30	0.05	Rejected
IAUE	361	3.41						

Source: SPSS Version 23 (2026)

The data in table 1.3 showed that t-calculated value of 1.88 at 430 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, with the t-critical value 1.516. The null hypothesis was not accepted because t-critical is greater than the t-calculated. This implies that there is significant difference to the mean ratings of Business Education students’ Business in Rivers State Universities and Ignatius Ajuru University of

Education on the extent to which Business Education students' perceive Artificial Intelligence (AI) challenges in Business Education in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Business Education students in Rivers Universities and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Business Education students' perceive negative toward entrepreneurial practices in Rivers State Universities. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Business Education students in Rivers Universities and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which Business Education students' perceive Internet of Things (IoT) challenges in Rivers State Universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from research questions 1 The study found that artificial intelligence (AI) significantly helps in reducing challenges in Business Education by enhancing personalized learning, improving students' understanding of complex business concepts, and providing intelligent tutoring systems that independent learning. This indicates that AI contributed positively to overcoming instructional and learning difficulties faced by Business Education students in Rivers State Universities revealed that from the qualitative data analyzed, artificial intelligence is moderately applied. This findings is in agreement with the view of Chaudhury (2017), who opened that artificial intelligence is beneficial for both students and teachers as it creates an educational environment and provides collaboration learning. In agreement with the view of Chaudhary, Fernandez, Fernandez, and Abule (2019), optioned that the use of artificial technologies helps teachers and students to gain more educational experience and provide information for teachers in the management of educational practices. In agreement with to view of Chaudhary, Fernandez, Fernandez, and Aburto, Amuge, (2023) who stated artificial intelligence is the ability of a digital computer to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligence beings like humans. In agreement with the view of Chaudhary, Fernandez, Fernandez, and Aburto, Amuge, Singh, Khan, and Khan (2023) stated that chatGPT offers a personalized learning experience, enabling students to emerge with content tailored to their unique needs and pace, enhancing the overall educational process without replacing teachers. In agreement with the view of Chaudhary, Fernandez, Fernandez, and Aburto, Amuge, Grajeda, Burgos, Cordova and Sangilines, (2024) stated that the integration of artificial intelligence is revolutionizing higher education by personalizing the learning experience to meet the diverse needs and styles of students. In the same direction Copeland (2024) stated that artificial intelligence has the ability to perform tasks commonly associated with human beings. The researcher is of the view that Business Educator should give students individualized training and fill in knowledge through self-directed learning. Also, Artificial intelligence blends robust datasets with computer science to be able to create functions that solve problems.

Internet of Things (IoT)

To study also revealed that the Internet of Things (IoT) plays a significant role in internet learning challenges in Business Education by promoting real-time access to learning resources, improving practical learning experiences through smart devices, and enhancing communication between students and learning system. This shows that IoT positively supports effective teaching and learning systems process in Business Education in Rivers State Universities revealed that from qualitative data analyzed, internet of Things is moderately applied by Business Education student. This findings is in agreement with the view of Keyur and Sunil (2016) who optioned in a world where billions of objects can sense, and share information, all interconnected over public or private internet protocol (IP) networks, these interconnected objects have data regularly connected, analyzed, and used to initiate action, providing a wealth of intelligence for planning, management, and decision-making. This is the world of the internet of things (IoT). In agreement with the view of keyur and Sunil, Coursera, (2023) stated that the Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of physical devices. These devices can transfer data to one another without human intervention. IoT devices are not limited to computers or machinery. This findings is in agreement with the view of Coursera. Saaudi, et al, (2023) stated that the educational sector is always at the forefront of sectors that employ modern technologies and their service, as this sector represents the main pillar upon which the trends of the knowledge economy are built, which is the most prominent front for major

economies in the tinning years. In agreement with the view of Saaudi, et al, Alexander (2024) stated that IoT is a network of interrelated devices that connect and exchange data with other IoT devices and the load. The internet of Things (IoT) encompasses electronic, communication, computer service, and engineering.

CONCLUSION

Emerging trends and challenges in Business Education reflect the dynamic changes taking place in the global trends economical business environment. The study has shown that emerging trends such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), digital learning platforms, and other Innovative technologies have significance transposed teaching and learning services in Business Education. These trends have improved access to informative, enhance their economical delivery, promoted skill acquisition, and prepared students for modern workplace devices. They have also contributed to more interactive, flexible, and student-centered learning environments, thereby improving the overall quality of Business Education.

However, despite these positive developments, several challenges continue to hinder the full integration and effective utilization of these emerging trends. These challenges include inadequate technological infrastructure, lack of digital skills among educators and students, insufficient funding, resistance to change, and high cost of implementing advanced technologies such as AI and IoT. These limitations reduce the extent to which institutions can only study benefit from the opportunities provided by emerging trends in Business Education. Emerging trends offer significant benefits for improving the effectiveness and relevance of Business Education, their successful implementation depends on addressing the existing challenges. Trends there is a need for continuous investment of these technologies. This will ultimately enhance the capacity of Business Education exist their prepare students for the demands of the modern digital economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion down from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Business Education departments in Rivers State Universities should identify the integration of artificial intelligence tools such as intelligent tutoring systems and AI-based learning platforms into teaching and learning processes. This will future enhance personalized learning, improve students' understanding of complex business concepts, and support independent learning, thereby reducing instructional challenges in in Business Educators
2. Business Education department should promote the adoption of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and smart learning systems in classroom and laboratories to enhance real-time access to learning students and learning systems, thereby strengthening effective teaching and learning processes in Business Education.

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